

Balancing Traditional Religious Principles with Modern Legal Concepts and Its Reflection in the Constitutional Underpinning: A Comparative Analysis of Criminal Law in Egypt and Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

This study analyzes the constitutional underpinnings of substantive criminal law in Egypt and Saudi Arabia. Because of their shared Islamic heritage, the two influential Middle Eastern states have developed distinct legal frameworks reflecting their unique historical, cultural, and political contexts.

The aim of research is investigate how traditional values and contemporary legal models are incorporated in the criminal justice systems of Egypt and Saudi Arabia; this applies specifically to their constitutional setups, typologies of offenses, and new laws that have come into effect.

The research entails both the analysis of primary sources such as constitutions and codes of laws, and other secondary sources such as textbooks, journal articles, or other textual discourses in order to investigate the four components of. How cumulative criminalization developed with history; constitutional overview; split of criminal justice intricacies; incorporation of changes pertained in prospects of changes in laws for quality and reliability of our findings.

Results reveal the difference between Egypt of the pharaohs, which was situated around the river Nile, and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as the former displays a system intermediate between Western and Islamic laws, while the latter is predominantly Islamic law-oriented. Both countries face difficulties in the process of reconciling their legal systems with respect to human rights; although such issues are diverse in nature, and range in severity.

This study where it seeks to examine and compare the substantive criminal law of two of the biggest countries in the Middle East in each and every aspect. It provides insights, on how nations that are Islamic in nature have organized their systems of justice by incorporating the ancient traditions with the contemporary ones. This new approach will undoubtedly intrigue a professional

Keywords: constitutional underpinnings, criminal law, substantive law, Egypt, Saudi Arabia

1. Introduction

The two countries Egypt and Saudi Arabia being the great penetration of Islamic religion in their systems of laws show several practices of law in comparison. In these countries' legal systems, Egypt is more a blend consisting of Islamic law, mixed with emphasis on borrowings from the French traditions of law and including some elements of ancient as well as modern Egyptian law^[1]. This amalgamation, However, is reflective of the Transformations that have been conducted within Egypt as one who has gone through colonialism and then post-colonialism. In contrast^[2], to that approach is Saudi Arabia's commitment, to incorporating the Qur'an and Islamic customs into its

system in a straightforward manner while retaining numerous traditional Arabic legal terms and ideas.

The development of systems, in Egypt and Saudi Arabia sheds light on the issues faced by Islamic countries in today's world. According to Alkhedhairi (2023)^[3] there is an effort to reconcile religious beliefs, with modern legal ideas and global human rights norms. Nevertheless, there is a lack of research addressing how these struggles are directly manifested in the principles governing criminal justice in Egypt and Saudi Arabia.

This study seeks to fill this void by examining the research inquiries.

Q1:What are the variations, in the approach to law, between the constitutional structures of Egypt and Saudi Arabia?

Q2:What significant variances exist in the classification and handling of offenses, between the two nations? How have the changes, in both countries aimed to update their criminal justice systems while preserving their Islamic heritage?

Q3:What obstacles do Egypt and Saudi Arabia encounter when they attempt to synchronize their systems, with human rights norms?

This study aims to explore how Islamic nations balance updating their frameworks with upholding their religious values by delving into these inquiries This comparative examination of how Egypt and Saudi Arabia handle this issue provides important perspectives on the different routes that Islamic nations can take when enhancing their criminal justice systems These findings address a significant void, in existing comparative legal studies that concentrate on the Middle East

2. Methodology

The research uses an examination of legal materials, like constitutions and criminal laws in Egypt and Saudi Arabia to compare and analyze them effectively. To add depth and understanding to the analysis process secondary sources such as literature are also considered. The study delves into four aspects; the evolution of law over times historical aspect; the legal frameworks within the constitutions; how crimes are structured and classified; in terms of criminality; recent changes made to the laws along, with obstacles faced. In every country, both the rules of law and their practical application in real life help to achieve completeness of the understanding of legal environments^[4, 5 & 6].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Historical Development of Criminal Law

The development of law from the beginning and till today can be viewed as a certain timeline where there have been many achievements along the way.

The development of laws, in Egypt and Saudi Arabia has followed paths over time with unique legal progressions noted in each country's history. In Egypt's case specifically the legal framework has seen changes since the adoption of its modern constitution in 1923^[7].

This evolution represents a progressive trend toward the establishment of a secular order while preserving certain important Islamic values. It is evident that throughout its development, the structure of Egyptian criminal code and the procedural subject have borrowed a lot from French and British traditions.

Saudi Arabia's legal system has held onto its roots in law compared to other countries in contrast, to the captured information^[8]. The enactment of the Basic Law of Governance back in 1992 formalized these core beliefs by emphasizing the dominance of Sharia law within a constitutional framework structure.

3.2 Constitutional Frameworks

The distinct methodology which Egypt and Saudi Arabia employ in their legal systems to respond to crime and criminality is indicative of the respective levels of legal apprehension. The Constitution of Egypt adopted in 2014 is the one enshrined with the principles of the human rights policy of the executive and provision of all forms of fair trial. In this respect, Rashdan (2023)^[9] looks at Article 95 of the Egyptian Constitution talks about presumption of innocence and states that everyone is innocent until proven guilty and article 96 states that everyone has the right to be heard in a court of law. These provisions bear evidence of Egypt's aspiration, to bring its system into the order with the international standards of the criminal justice.

Saudi Arabia's Basic Law of Governance stresses on the necessity of Sharia as a source of authority while addressing the issue of the safeguarding of fundamental freedoms in as far as Islamic Sharia is concerned under Article 26 of the Basic Law which provides a different perspective on criminal law than that of Egypt^[10]. This glaring difference in intervention has got many repercussions on the way criminal law has been developed and practiced in either countries.

3.3 Structure and Categorization of Criminal Crimes

The classification of crimes in Egypt and Saudi Arabia also depicts the distinct development trajectories of their legal systems. The Penal Code of Egypt outlined by Nouh (2023)^[11] divides crimes into three classes which are felonies, misdemeanors and contravention. This division of crimes into three degrees evokes Western legal systems and it is as a result of historical influence and the quest for easing the legal system in Egypt. Saudi Arabia, on the other hand, has adopted an entirely different system of classification in its penal code. Crimes are classified into Hudud (offences having preset punishments as stated in the Quran), Qisas (offences causing physical injury or harm), Ta'zir (offences with adjustable sentences) and administrative offences prescribed in the bylaws^[12]. It can thus be noted that this classifying system shows that Saudi Arabia prefers to enforce laws that are very much in line with Islamic laws.

3.4 Recent Reforms and Challenges

Still, both Egypt and Saudi Arabia have recently embraced a wave of legal changes. These transformations, however, vary in nature and dynamics. In the last few years for instance, attempts have been made on the changes in the Code of Criminal Procedure in Egypt to strengthen the due process. All these came about while steps were being taken towards the reforms of the penal code in order to deal with issues like cyber-crimes, terrorism, etc.^[13]. These developments are indicative

of the current situation in Egypt in which the government pursues a middle ground between civil liberties and national security.

Saudi Arabia has also implemented reforms, including, for instance, the introduction of the Anti-Cyber Crime Law in 2007 and changes to the judicial system, e.g., the establishment of specialized courts^[14]. Nevertheless, as Kelly (2023)^[15] underscores, Saudi Arabia, on the other hand, harbors structural problems that make the imposition of human rights law on its legal practice exceedingly difficult, for instance, in relations to corporal punishment and due process.

Both countries grapple with modernizing their legal systems while maintaining their cultural and religious identities. Egypt faces challenges in addressing issues such as overcrowding in prisons and pretrial detention^[16]. Saudi Arabia, meanwhile, must navigate the delicate process of codifying criminal laws while adhering to Sharia principles.

4. CONCLUSION

This comparative analysis reveals significant differences in the constitutional underpinnings of substantive criminal law between Egypt and Saudi Arabia. These differences reflect each nation's unique historical, cultural, and political contexts. Egypt's legal system demonstrates a more pronounced blend of Islamic and Western legal traditions, as evidenced by its constitution and criminal code structure. Saudi Arabia, in contrast, maintains a more vital adherence to traditional Islamic legal principles, though recent efforts have been made to codify and standardize their application.

The study highlights the complexity of legal reform in Islamic states, particularly in balancing traditional religious principles with modern legal concepts. Egypt's and Saudi Arabia's differing approaches provide valuable insights into the various paths Islamic countries may take in developing their criminal justice systems. Both nations face ongoing challenges in aligning their criminal justice systems with international human rights standards, albeit in different areas and to varying degrees.

Future research in this area could benefit from examining the practical implementation of legal reforms in both countries, analyzing the impact of international human rights treaties on domestic criminal law development in Islamic states, and investigating the role of judicial interpretation in shaping criminal law application in systems with various levels of codification.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the broader understanding of how Islamic states navigate the challenges of modernizing their legal systems while maintaining their cultural and religious identities. It underscores the importance of considering historical, cultural, and religious factors in comparative legal studies, particularly criminal law. As Egypt and Saudi Arabia continue to evolve their legal systems, their experiences offer valuable lessons for other nations seeking to balance tradition with modernity in their approach to criminal justice.

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